

INVESTIGATION ON THE FRACTURE AND INTERFACE
OF HIP C/Al COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

The dense C/Al composites have been fabricated by hot isostatic pressing (HIP) with which the C/Al precursor wires were encapsulated in a glass tube. It was observed that the fracture of the C/Al composite possesses a low strength and smoothness, and the reaction layer of the interface with scanning electron microscope (SEM). The transmission electron microscope (TEM) and X-ray energy spectroscopy (XES) were used to observe and determine the morphology and the composition of the interface. It was found the interface was divided into two layers. TiB_2 interface was diffused to the both sides of the interface and the compositions of the carbon fiber and matrix also were diffused through the interface. Besides, the electron diffraction (ED) was used to study the interface structure. The structure compositions were defined as TiO_2 , TiC , TiB_2 , $r-Al_2O_3$, Ti , B and C . The chemical compositions were analyzed by auger electron spectroscopy (AES) and second ion masses spectroscopy (SIMS). The composition determined were used by SIMS and ED with a nearly result except founding Al_4C_3 at SIMS.

INTRODUCTION

Chemical vapor deposition (CVD) is commonly used to produce the C/Al composite. The fibers were drawn through a CVD chamber where they were coated by TiB_2 deposit and then drawn through a molten bath of Al or its alloy for getting precursor wires. The C/Al precursor wires were used to fabricate the composite by hot pressing (HP)¹⁻⁴.

The composite fracture, strength and interface and degradation of the fiber strength have been widely investigated after HP⁵⁻⁹.

HIP is effective to manufacture the C/Al composite, but the changes of the interface during HIP process were poorly reported. The C/Al composite was fabricated by HIP using a vacuum glass tube in which the C/Al precursor wires were packed at a proper condition.

The equipments of SEM, XES, TEM, ED and AES and SIMS were used to investigate the fracture and interface of HIP C/Al composite with microchange. The composition between the specimens of HP and HIP was also made. It was found that there were not only the same reaction on the interface, but some new results were produced at the both sides of the interface of HIP C/Al composite. Therefore, the investigation of the interface became more important for manufacture C/Al composite.

EXPERIMENT

1. Manufacture of HIP C/Al composite

The C/Al-13Si precursor wires were packed in a glass tube which was pumped to 1.33 Pa before the one end of the glass tube was encapsulated with a fire. The glass tube sealed was up-set in the high pressure chamber of HIP. The process is carried out by pumping the chamber, gradual heating to 873K and slowly injecting a high pure Ar to 50 MPa during 30 min, then constanting the temperature and pressure for 15 min. The HIP/C/Al composite was fabricated with above said best conditions.

2. Observation and Measurement

The fracture of the C/Al composite was observed and the fracture morphology of SEM was used to compare with HP and liquid infiltration C/Al composite. The compositions of the interface nearby were measured.

The ion thinning technique was used to prepared the foil specimen for TEM. TiB_2 interface has been investigated by EM 400-T. XES was used to determine the interface and the both of the interface. The composition curves were drawn. On the other hand, the interface structure was measured by ED and the surface composition of TEM specimen was also indicated by AES and SIMS.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig.1 shows all of the morphology of HIP C/Al composite fracture. From the figure, we can see the specimen is very dense, because the specimen was pressed at the same pressure in any diraction during the temperature of the liquid phase. The carbon fibers were fully infiltrated by Al-13Si alloy so that the fibers pull-outed were nearly not found. From Fig.2, the smooth fracture appeared more clearly. It is shown that the bounding among the fiber-interface-matrix was strengthened during HIP. In

Fig.2, the crenellations around the fiber were formed by reacting between TiB_2 and Al-13Si. From Fig.3, the reaction layer was more clear, but this behaviour was not seen in the reference 9 because the C/Al composite was made by a solid-state diffusion bonding. Few fibers splitted explained that the interface bonding between TiB_2 -matrix and TiB_2 -fiber was bigger than the cross strength of the carbon fiber during cooling. The compositions of the three points were determined by XES from Fig.3 at the interface (point 1), core of the fiber (point 2) and matrix (point 3).

200 μ m

Fig.1 HIP C/Al composite fracture by SEM

10 μ m

Fig.2 HIP C/Al composite fracture
by SEM

5 μ m

Fig.3 HIP C/Al composite fracture
by SEM

Table 1 The composition of the fracture

Composition	point 1	point 2	point 3
Al Wt%	78.369	82.061	97.734
Si	20.085	16.785	1.831
Ti	0.902	0.485	0.435

The results were listed in table 1. The relative quantities of Ti are 0.942 (wt %), 0.485 and 0.435 which respectively belong to the interface, core of the fiber and matrix as showed in Fig.3. Difference among them is unobvious and the results is just the same as the reference 9, only the quantity of Ti is lower than it. It is probable that TiB_2 of the interface was diffused at HIP condition. The quantity of Si is very low at the third point with 1.831 Wt%, but it should be 13 Wt% for Al-13Si alloy. The segregation of Si is obvious, because the process during HIP is at a high temperature and pressure.

The ion thinning technique was employed to prepare TEM specimen for further understanding the change during HIP. Fig.4 is the interface of HIP C/Al composite by TEM. Al-13Si matrix, TiB_2 interface and the carbon fiber were showed in Fig.4. Fig.5 is the interface of HP Gr/Al composite. Generally, Fig.4 and Fig.5 are the same, but there are obvious differences when the micrographes are carefully observed. The interface is not only divided into two layers, but the new results of a reaction ribbon are also showed nearby in the carbon fiber side at Fig.4. The phenomenon is not viewed in Fig.5.

500A

Al-13Si TiB_2 C

500A

Al-13Si TiB_2 Gr

Fig.4 HIP C/Al composite interface by TEM

Fig.5 HP Gr/Al composite interface by TEM

The distributions of Al, Si and Ti were measured by XES at the perpendicular direction of TEM specimen over against the matrix, interface and carbon fiber. It was considered that the carbon composition was not collected at the side of the fiber so that the compositions were multiplied by 0.25 for correcting the compositions. The results can more closed to the real condition and it was showed as Fig.6 curves. The diffusion of Ti was easily viewed and the matrix Al-Si or C can also crossed each other. The spots nearby the interface of the carbon fiber were probably Al_4C_3 . From Fig.6, we can see the most quantity of Ti is 50 wt% at the interface, but the most quantity of Ti is over 65 wt% at the interface of HP Gr/Al composite.¹⁰ It explained that the diffusion was obviously showed during HIP.

Fig.6 The dispersion of Al, Si, Ti at the interface

Fig.7 is an electron diffraction patterns (EDP) of TEM specimen interface at difference area. Their structures were determined with the analysis of EDP. Fig.7-a is the patterns which were defined as Ti, TiO_2 and TiB_2 . Fig.7-b is the patterns which were indicated as TiC , TiB_2 , B, and $r-Al_2O_3$ and C. The patterns explained that the axial preferred orientation between the layers of TiB_2 and the carbon fiber is just the same direction and the c-axes of the hexagonal crystal of TiB_2 and carbon were overlapped. Therefore, these patterns are crossed each other. Moreover, there is common boundary in the crystals, and the defect is very poor.

AES and SIMS were also used to analyze the composition of TEM specimen for proving the resultants defined at the interface. The compositions of TiB_2 , Ti, B, C and TiO , TiO_2 and Al_4C_3 were showed at the interface area, and the bargraph of SIMS was exhibited in Fig.8. This result is

Fig.8 SIMS bargraph of the interface

generally the same as the analysis of EDP. The difference between them is that Al_4C_3 was confirmed in HIP C/Al composite by SIMS. Elements of C and Al crossed one another through the interface, because the barrier fractor of the interface has been destroyed.

CONCLUSIONS

1. HIP process is effective to manufacture C/Al composite and can be used to make dense specimen.

2. The fracture of the specimen is brittle and smooth. The C/Al composite is fabricated at the parameteres of 50 MPa and 873 K during 15 min.
3. The interface diffusion reaction of HIP C/Al composite is exhibited by TEM and the new results are formed nearby in the interface.
4. The consistes of the structure of the interface are defined as TiC, TiO₂, TiB₂, Ti, r-Al₂O₃, B and C by EDP.
5. The compositions of TiB₂, Ti, B, C and TiO, TiO₂ and Al₄C₃ are showed at the interface by SIMS.

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